

IRIM3D 2025 Workshop Proposal:

Industry 5.0: Workplace Transformation with Next Generation Smart Robots

Industry 5.0 brings humans back to the center of industrial production through effective human-robot collaboration. While collaborative robots enable shared workspaces, true integration requires more than safety certification. This workshop explores practical challenges and recent advances in perception, control, and motion planning to bridge the gap between lab research and real-world deployment.

1. Workshop Title Industry 5.0: Workplace Transformation with Next Generation Smart Robots

2. Organisers

- Matteo Dalle Vedove, Università degli Studi di Trento, *matteo.dallevedove@unitn.it*;
- Edoardo Lamon, Università degli Studi di Trento, *edoardo.lamon@unitn.it*;
- Daniele Fontanelli, Università degli Studi di Trento, *daniele.fontanelli@unitn.it*;

3. Workshop Format

The tentative schedule of the workshop is:

1. Introduction (5 minutes): overview of workshop themes, illustrated with practical examples from the EU-funded Magician and Inverse projects;
2. 6 Keynote Talks (14 minutes each): each keynote will address a key-enabling technology for Industry 5.0, or how those concepts can be transferred to the state-of-the-art in the automation industry. Each talk comprises a 12 minute presentation and 2 minutes for Q&A;

4. Workshop Objectives and Main Topics

The workshop aims at disseminating recent research advancements on smart robotic solutions in Industry 5.0. Rather than being vertical on a specific topic, the workshop will present a broad and diverse selection of research areas, with strong focus on the practical implementation to bring academia closer to the industry needs. Topics of interest include:

- advanced sensing systems and algorithms for smart factories;
- safe robot control in physical human-robot interactive tasks;
- shared autonomy and adaptive control to balance human expertise and robotic consistency;
- human-aware motion prediction and planning in collaborative and cooperative environments;
- learning from human demonstration to enhance productivity and flexibility;
- reinforcement learning and large behavioural models for industrial settings;
- next-generation task allocation and planning in human-robot teams.

5. Keywords Industrial Robotics, Industry 5.0, Human-Robot Collaboration, Safe Control, Learning from Demonstration.

6. Preferred Date Confirmed speaker provided a stronger preference of having the workshop on Friday the 17th of October.

7. List of Speakers

List of speaker (not in order):

- Marco Todescato, Fraunhofer Italia (confirmed);
- Marta Lorenzini, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (confirmed);
- Riccardo Caccavale, Università degli Studi di Napoli "Federico II" (confirmed);
- Stefano Ghidoni, Università degli studi di Padova (confirmed);
- Francesca Negrello, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (not confirmed);
- Antonio Frisoli, Next Generation Robotics (contacted, not yet confirmed);

8. Expected Number of attendees We have no prior experience in organising an I-RIM 3D workshop, but we expect 20-30 people.

9. Target Audience The workshop targets a broad audience interested in smart manufacturing and Industry 5.0, including:

- robotics and control researchers looking to understand industrial requirements;
- industry professionals seeking insight into upcoming technologies;
- students and early-career scientists eager to explore interdisciplinary applications.

10. Workshop Outcomes All accepted manuscripts and accompanying posters, upon confirmation from the authors, will be published in the workshop webpage to further disseminate the works.

11. Plan for Special Issue or Session No special issue is currently planned. Based on workshop feedback, we are interested in organising a longer-format session or special track at larger venues.

12. Call for Extended Abstracts We will organise a call for abstracts addressing the workshop theme, using the same template and rules of the main event. All accepted works will be reviewed (single-blinded) by the organisation committee, and will have the possibility to disseminate their work through a poster presentation. The top 3 submission will also be eligible for a 5 minute oral presentation.

13. Workshop Webpage <https://idra-lab.github.io/IRIM3D-manufacturing-workshop/>

14. Notes on Registration The 2 free one-day registrations will be assigned using the following policy:

1. invited speakers who do not register for the main IRIM3D event;
2. organizing committee members not otherwise registered;
3. authors of accepted abstracts who are not registered for IRIM3D.